

Lessons Learned from Vegetation Stability Indicators Applied to Individual Vegetation Types

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Abstract: There is a growing need to optimize conservation efforts in the face of widespread habitat loss and climate change. We explored the utility of an existing indicator framework encompassing ten indicators representing matches and mismatches between current and potential vegetation estimates. Using Hungary as a case study, the framework was applied to three vegetation types: *Artemisia* salt steppes, swamp forests, and beech forests. The spatial distribution of indicators revealed patterns of stability, degradation, and restoration potential. *Artemisia* salt steppes were largely stable in their core range but showed signs of instability and vegetation inertia in certain western and central regions within Hungary. Swamp forests exhibited strong regional variation, while beech forests were mostly confined to climatically suitable mountainous regions, with high stability overall, though some marginal and western populations showed signs of instability possibly linked to climate change. Exploring the spatial pattern of these indicators provided valuable spatial insights into vegetation condition, highlighting areas of high conservation value, instability, and restoration opportunity. The framework shows potential for guiding conservation planning, supporting habitat restoration, and informing land-use decisions by identifying where the specific vegetation types are self-sustaining versus where intervention may be needed.

Keywords: habitat stability indicators; potential natural vegetation; conservation prioritisation; restoration targets.

1 Introduction

Natural habitats have been destroyed, fragmented or transformed worldwide due to human land use (Newbold et al. 2015, Allan et al. 2017, Lawrence et al. 2021) and anthropogenic climate change (Segan et al. 2016). Therefore, the protection of remaining habitats, or the restoration of habitats at suitable locations is one of the main focuses in nature conservation. But since the sources are typically limited, conservation efforts need to be optimized. This creates a need to acquire accurate information on the state of natural vegetation, because conservation goals can be fulfilled if the target vegetation will be self-sustaining in the long term.

Here, we apply our indicator framework which relies on the matches and mismatches of the potential and actual distribution on vegetation (Gyalus et al. under review). The potential vegetation was based on the predictions of

multiple potential natural vegetation (MPNV) models, developed by Somodi et al. (2017). This is the expansion of the concept of potential natural vegetation (Tüxen 1956), the vegetation able to survive without human intervention at a given location with given environmental conditions. We present the spatial distribution of the indicators on maps of selected vegetation types and interpret the information in the patterns to demonstrate the applicability of our proposed indicators.

2 Materials and methods

We used the Hungarian vegetation as a case study for our indicators. The actual vegetation is based on the GIS Database of the Hungarian Habitats (MÉTA in Hungarian, Molnár et al. 2008). The MÉTA survey was conducted between 2003 and 2006, presence-absence of (semi)natural vegetation was assessed by field observation. The database covers the whole area of Hungary with a hexagonal grid system, with 35 ha cell size (approx. ~700 m diameter), embedded in a grid of 5.5*6.5 km quadrats. A total of 199 MÉTA quadrats had no observations and were excluded. These quadrats are masked out with grey on the maps.

The potential natural vegetation predictions were produced by gradient boosting models, as described in detail by Somodi et al. (2017, 2024). This study resulted in estimates for 39 potential natural vegetation (PNV) and 8 potential replacement vegetation (PRV) types (Chytrý 1998). The raw probability estimates were rescaled into a 5-level ordinal scale within each vegetation type to ensure comparability between different types.

Matches and mismatches of the binary observation (act0-1) and 5-scale prediction (pot0-4) values were identified per spatial unit. The combination of matches and mismatches yielded 10 possible indicators, visualized on maps of three vegetation types as examples. The names and interpretations of individual indicators are as follows (Table 1).

Table 1. Names, abbreviations and interpretation of indicators. Modified from Gyalus et al. 2026.

name	abbreviation	interpretation
unsuitability1	act0pot0	unsuitable site – matrix
unsuitability2	act0pot1	unsuitable site closer to suitability - less hostile matrix
uncertain potential	act0pot2	uncertain environment, may be possible to establish
potential site	act0pot3	confirmed suitability
exceptional potentiality	act0pot4	confirmed above-average suitability
extreme inertia	act1pot0	extremely unsuitable presence (no example in the case study)
vegetation inertia	act1pot1	instability / low quality, strong indication of vegetation inertia
uncertain fate	act1pot2	questionable suitability, possible vegetation inertia
sustainable presence	act1pot3	high suitability, high conservation values
exceptionally strong presence	act1pot4	outstanding suitability, indication for high conservation value at spot

3 Results

Artemisia salt steppes are mainly distributed east of the Tisza River, where stands occupy large continuous areas with sustainable (act1pot3) or especially strong presence (act1pot4) (Figure 1). High potentiality sites are in-between or nearby these existing high-quality stands. Unstable (act1pot2) stands nearby the main distribution area are typically smaller patches. However, there is a higher concentration of unstable stands in the Danube-Tisza Interfluvium (middle Hungary) and patches with vegetation inertia are located west from the Danube, in Mezőföld.

Larger areas hosting swamp forests are present in Kisalföld, Somogy, Danube-Tisza Interfluvium and Nyírség, other occurrences are small and isolated. The latter also exhibits vegetation inertia (act1pot1) (Figure 2). Vegetation inertia and unstable (act1pot2) patches concentrate in the Danube-Tisza Interfluvium and at the fringes of the more stable stands. High potentiality absence locations

(act0pot3, act0pot4) can be found typically between patches of high quality (act1pot3, act1pot4) presences. A wide band of potential sites with south-north orientation can also be found in the northeast, in the Nyírség region. The distribution of indicators shows that beech forests are most likely present in the higher mountains, where high quality stands (act1pot3, act1pot4) occur in many adjacent spatial units (Figure 3). The unstable (act1pot2) and stands showing inertia (act1pot1) are at the fringes of the more stable populations, or in isolated smaller patches, but their proportion is generally higher west to the Danube. Absence locations with high potentiality (act0pot3, act0pot4) are sparse and can be found in gaps of good quality stands. The lower altitude regions of the country do not appear suitable for beech forests.

Figure 1. Distribution of indicators for Artemisia salt steppes.

Figure 2. Distribution of indicators for swamp forests.

Figure 3. Distribution of indicators for beech forests.

4 Discussion

Map representation of indicators of vegetation types convey important spatial information which support conservation and restoration planning or even economic decision (e.g. forestry).

The status of *Artemisia* salt steppes as vegetation type is stable on a country scale. However, the stands in Mezőföld (west from Danube) and the southern ones in Danube-Tisza Interfluvium are less stable than the ones east of the Tisza River. According to Lendvai (2023), the flora of alkaline and saline soils in Mezőföld has remarkable differences from the eastern ones (Lendvai 2023), so these stands represent landscape-level diversity.

In case of swamp forests, we can see significant regional differences again: the patches in the southern parts of Danube-Tisza Interfluvium are unstable or in vegetation inertia while the stands of other regions are self-sustaining. Járai-Komlódi (1959) reported the degradation of swamp

forests in this region due to drying of the region and predicted their slow transformation into riverine oak-elm-ash forests. Later studies confirmed these predictions, many of these stands progressed further in this direction (Molnár et al. 1997). Since these stands again represent a regional subtype, their restoration – if possible – could greatly support landscape diversity.

The distribution of indicators at beech forests shows that present occurrences concentrate in the higher parts of the medium mountains, coinciding with the climate zones optimal for beech in Hungary. The area of beech forests increased since the 2nd world war after the forestry practice of pine and oak plantation on beech optimum climate ceased (Bartha et al. 2024), so this vegetation type has already reoccupied most of the suitable locations. This is apparent in the continuous present cover: high potential absence locations (act0pot3, act0pot4) are sparse and can be found in gaps of good quality stands. The higher proportion of unstable or stands with vegetation inertia west to the Danube, which might be a consequence of

ongoing climate change (Mátyás et al. 2010, Bede-Fazekas et al. 2017, Illés and Móricz 2022, Bartha et al. 2025).

5 Conclusions

The cases of individual vegetation types demonstrated that the indicator framework effectively links actual and potential vegetation patterns and thereby identifies spatial differences in habitat suitability, stability, and restoration potential. The case studies of the three Hungarian vegetation type distribution highlighted both the strengths and the limits of the framework, which can be summed up in a few key points:

- Stable and high-quality stands concentrated in core regions of the specific vegetation type: *Artemisia* salt steppes east of the Tisza River, swamp forests in Kisalföld and Nyírség, and beech forests in core mountainous areas.
- Unstable stands and vegetation inertia typically occurred at the margins of core habitats or in isolated patches, indicating areas that may be more vulnerable to degradation, fragmentation, or changing environmental conditions. Furthermore, unstable stands for beech specifically appeared to concentrate at the climatic limit of the habitat's distribution.
- Areas with high potentiality but current absence of the locally suitable vegetation often lie between or near existing high-quality stands, suggesting important opportunities for habitat restoration, connectivity improvement, and future conservation planning.

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